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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D22: Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation Report v1.0

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Executive Summary

The CODECO Deliverable D22 - *Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation Report v1.0* covers the dissemination, engagement towards industry and academia, and standardisation actions that have been developed in the first eighteen months of the CODECO project, under the umbrella of WP6.

Throughout the first period of CODECO (M1-M18), a variety of activities were done to effectively communicate project objectives, promote its achievements, engage with the scientific community, and establish standardization practices. This report highlights the CODECO's strategies employed, activities conducted, and outcomes achieved in each of these key areas and corresponds to a first regular report on CODECO dissemination, communication, and standardization activities.

Keywords: Cloud, Communication, Dissemination, Edge, Internet of Things, Internetworking, Network Technologies, Open Source, Promotion, Software, Visibility.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
AR	CODECO Stakeholder group Academia and Research
ATH	CODECO partner ATHENA
CA	Consortium Agreement
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CONASENSE	6G Communications Navigation, Sensing and Services platform
DEV	CODECO Stakeholder group developers
Dx	Deliverable x
EC	European commission
EUCEI	EUCloudEdgeIoT initiative
EUS	CODECO Stakeholder group End-users
FOR	CODECO partner fortiss GmbH
GA	General Audience
GOV	Policy makers and regional entities
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
INO	INOVA +
IoT	Internet of Things
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputer Centre
Mx	Month x of the CODECO project
N/A	Not Available
N.a.	Not applicable
OA	Open Access
OSS	Open-Source Software
PC	Project coordinator (FOR)
PDLC	CODECO Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning
SDO	Standards Development Organization
SJR	Scimago Journal and Country Rank
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SWM	CODECO Seamless Workload Migration component
TPC	Technical Programme Committee
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UGOE	University of Göttingen
WPL	Work Package Leader
WPx	Work Package x

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1 Introduction

The main purpose of the CODECO Deliverable *D22 - Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation Report v1.0* is to provide a description on the project communication, dissemination and standardisation activities and achievements developed between M1 and M18 of the project. D22 follows the plan presented in M3, in Deliverable D3 (Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan) [1].

1.1 Objectives

The CODECO Deliverable *D22 – Dissemination, Promotion, Scientific Outreach and Standardisation Report v1.0* serves as a documentation of the strategies employed and outcomes achieved regarding the dissemination of project findings, promotion of cognitive computing technologies, engagement in scientific outreach activities, and contribution to standardization efforts within the cognitive computing domain for the period being reported (M1-M18).

It aims to demonstrate the project's achievements and its impact with in scientific and industrial community, standardisation institutions and among broader stockholders. It serves to ensure that the project's results are communicated.

The document also mentions the involvement of various entities such as ICT companies, SMEs, government and public authorities, standardization bodies, academic and research institutions, end-users, and software developers in the project's exploitation activities and community building.

1.2 Deliverable Scope

D22 follows D21 [1] in terms of strategic dissemination, communication, engagement, and standardisation actions. It corresponds to an intermediate report, being its follow-up and final report D23 due in M36.

D22 covers the following aspects:

- **Report on dissemination of project results:** To disseminate the results of CODECO and make them accessible to relevant stakeholders and the public. D22 provides a list of results achieved, and their impact.
- **Report on awareness raised to the CODECO development:** To reach, stimulate and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that the results of the project are effectively highlighted, leading to validation, improvement and further adoption of the developed technologies and concepts, especially towards target vertical sectors, facilitating exploitation of the project's outcomes. This is described regarding scientific and industrial outreach activities that have been developed in the context of CODECO.
- **Report on promoting collaboration and synergies:** To create interest in the project among potential partners, investors, and other stakeholders, and to encourage them to get involved. CODECO has been developing synergies and collaborative actions with other ongoing projects to increase visibility, build partnerships and maximize impact.
- **Report on impact:** To ensure that the project has the highest possible impact and contributes to developments in the field. Exploitation strategies to outreach CODECO's results during and after the end of the project will be defined in the context of WP7.

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1.3 Structure

D22 has been developed in the context of WP6 - Dissemination, Promotion and Standardization, led by UGOE.

D22 covers the following aspects:

- The dissemination channels used to share project findings.
- The promotion efforts undertaken to raise awareness of CODECO solutions.
- The scientific outreach activities conducted to engage with relevant stakeholders.
- The contributions made to standardization bodies and efforts.
- The results and impact of the CODECO project for the period being reported.

The structure of this Deliverable can be described as follows:

- **Section 2** summarizes the CODECO target stakeholders, to better position the reader in the actions described in the subsequent sections.
- **Section 3** presents the dissemination and communication strategy and activities and details the channels used for disseminating project findings, within the period 1 of the project (M1-M18).
- **Section 4** presents the activities where CODECO engaged to achieve broad scientific and innovation outreach.
- **Section 5** covers standardisation activities in CODECO, including the CODECO standardization strategy and plan, and initial contributions achieved from M1-M18.
- **Section 6** summarizes the impact achieved by the activities pursued.
- **Section 7** presents the follow-up activities already in action, or agreed in the consortium, to be developed during the second period of CODECO (M19-M36), with particular focus in 2024.
- **Section 8** concludes the deliverable.

1.4 Dependencies

D22 corresponds to a report that updates the plan for communication, dissemination and outreach provided in D21 [1], month 3 (M3) of CODECO.

2 CODECO Target Stakeholders

D22 will ensure that the project's scientific and innovative results and outcomes are effectively disseminated among CODECO stakeholder groups, considering the specific domains addressed in the use cases and extending beyond them. The objective is to enhance the project's visibility and impact, highlighting its scientific significance and commercial potential. In this respect, the CODECO project identified several target stakeholders, which are summarized next.

- **Information and communication technologies (ICT)**, industrial and small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) players. This group comprises vendors and integrators, both large companies and SMEs, involved in the deployment of Cloud based and Edge based solutions, technology vendors, service providers, telecommunications operators, large companies, and SMEs. The aim is to raise CODECO awareness and to show its performance as well as a value-add. In this context it is relevant to highlight that both the industrial partners and the research partners play a key role in the further engagement of other industry players.

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- **Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers (GOV):** This group comprises a wide group of public sector stakeholders including government agencies, regulators, municipalities, citizens, public authorities, and other organizations which benefit from a platform such as CODECO to simplify the deployment of the containerized codebase.
- **Standardization entities and open-source communities (SDO):** Standardization entities responsible for defining and maintaining standards for various industries and technologies will ensure interoperability and compatibility with the CODECO framework. Normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia will collaborate on the development and adoption of modern technologies and open-source software, relevant to the CODECO ecosystem.
- **Academia and Research (AR):** Research scientists, teachers, and students in the field of computer science, engineering, and related disciplines will be a key group to spread the benefits of the CODECO concept, and to provide feedback and transfer of information, promoting scientific and technical know-how generated within the project. AR is a key group to spread the benefits of CODECO concepts and technologies, and to provide feedback to, transfer and promote the scientific and technical know-how generated within the project. This target group can be effectively reached through the consortium's research communities and partnerships with other leading research initiatives and institutions in Europe and beyond. It is relevant to highlight that both the industrial partners and the research partners play a key role in the further engagement of other industry players.
- **End-users (EUS):** The public and specific end-users in the use-case domains (Manufacturing, Smart Cities, Energy, Smart Buildings) play a major role in the project dissemination and engagement. This group includes consumers, who are interested in learning about the latest developments in Edge-Cloud computing and IoT and how these technologies will impact their lives.
- **Developers (DEV):** Software developers and early developers with whom CODECO shall interact via the activities developed in WP5 (use-cases), WP6 (dissemination, communication) and WP7 (community building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for third-party engagement). will also be considered to promote and test the CODECO toolkit and accelerate the integration of knowledge.
- **General Audience (GA):** General audience may also be considered as stakeholders of CODECO. Even without a specialized background in the technical areas of the project, they may still be interested in CODECO and understanding its potential implications for society.

3 Public Dissemination and Communication

This section describes the overall communication and dissemination activities carried out in the first part of CODECO (M1 – M18). The section starts by updates provided to the visual identity of the project (which has already been detailed in D21 [1]). Activities concerning public dissemination and communication are handled in CODECO in Task 6.1, under the leadership of partner INO.

3.1 Visual Identity of the Project

Aspects concerning the visual identity of the project were developed initially and have been described in D21 (M3), having also been subject of regular updates such as:

- Improvements to the templates launched in M1 and in use in the project due to disclaimers, or better automatization.
- Project logotype, released in M1.
- Project Website, released in M1.
- Social media, released in M1 and regularly updated via T6.1, INO.

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- Brochures and leaflets, provided by partner fortiss (FOR) and developed in cooperation with other entities.
- Infographics/Flyers, provided by Inova (INO) and FOR.
- Roll-up, provided by FOR.
- Multimedia content such as videos, developed by all partners in the context of use-cases, presentations of CODECO.
- Presentations developed for the sake of communication and by all projects, for the sake of representation and engagement of stakeholders.

Importantly, these materials are available in various formats, both print and digital, to ensure maximum accessibility for all stakeholders via the CODECO Website¹. All material is also available to the CODECO consortium via the project internal repository (rf. to **06-Marketing/Templates**).

The dissemination materials will continue to be regularly throughout the project's lifetime, and they will be promoted through the project's Website, social media channels, and other dissemination activities, and will be readily available for download or distribution as needed.

3.2 Project Website

The CODECO Website has been updated consistently since M1 to accompany the project's developments and milestones. As stated in D21, updates have been developed periodically (every 4 months), with particular focus in the most dynamic sections, namely, "News" and "List of Events" sections, making sure visitors can get the freshest information about the latest CODECO advancements. As the project evolves, and new initiatives are launched, the homepage header is adapted accordingly. For example, CODECO has now launched its *Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme*², a crucial part of its engagement strategy with the project's main stakeholders. As such, a new tab on the Website header was created, calling attention to the newly released initiative, and directly leading visitors to a comprehensive explanation of the action and the available opportunities.

Punctual improvements to the Website's aesthetics were also made, such as the section headers. To enhance accessibility to CODECO's social media, it was decided to place QR codes for LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube in the Contact section.

Follow us on CODECO's social media accounts

Scan the QR codes to get updates on the CODECO Project!

Figure 1: QR codes for CODECO social media in the Website's Contact section.

To evaluate the effectiveness of our communication and dissemination efforts, we are regularly monitoring the number of visitors to the project website. As indicated in Table 1, the

¹ <https://he-codeco.eu/branding/>

² <https://he-codeco.eu/ircep/>

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current metrics demonstrate a positive and exponential growth, significantly surpassing the expected yearly *Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)*.

Table 1: Number of visitors to the project website.

Dissemination Activity	KPI	Current metrics (Jan - June 2024)
Project Website	>500 visitors per year	826 visitors

We strongly believe that the excellent performance of the project’s social media, detailed next, has significantly driven traffic to the project website, greatly enhancing its visibility.

3.3 Social Media

CODECO relies on different social media to reach a broader audience and build a community of followers interested in its activities, as has been detailed in D21.

Overall, social media engagement has been very positive on both LinkedIn and X, with LinkedIn showing a particularly strong performance. We attribute this difference to LinkedIn's platform, where the CODECO partners can more effectively leverage their professional networks to disseminate CODECO materials, leading to a higher reach and more meaningful interactions with the content.

Regarding X, the growth hasn't been as steady as on LinkedIn. However, given the differences in tools and features between the platforms, the CODECO partners are adapting their strategy on X. We are now focusing on utilizing more hashtags related to CODECO keywords and actively retweeting relevant content within the network.

Table 2: CODECO social media metrics since January 2023.

X	Total	LinkedIn	Total
Retweets	80	Reposts	24
Likes	174	Reactions	980
Replies	3	Comments	21
Followers	123	Followers	483

CODECO social media KPI: >200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn

4 Broad Scientific and Innovation Outreach

In CODECO, the wider impacts concerning science and innovation are handled in the context of T6.2, led by partner University of Göttingen (UGOE), and involving all CODECO partners. In addition to regular scientific publications, CODECO has proposed to organize specific industrial and technical events: a first inception event (M12, FOR), focused on research and development, intended to create awareness among companies and especially SMEs about the project technical ambition and its potential commercial and market value and at least two scientific events (one Dagstuhl seminar, UGOE, and one scientific workshop, ATH co-located to a large conference, M24) to assist in reaching engagement of stakeholders from academia, being the value-add the possibility to increase exploitation opportunities. This section provides an overview on the achievements in this context developed from M1 until M18 of CODECO.

4.1 Scientific Publications

Scientific and academic publications play an important role in communicating the results of the CODECO project to two main target stakeholders (rf. to section 2), AR and ICT, and are critical for establishing the project's impact and reputation.

The CODECO consortium aims at publishing their findings in high-quality, peer-reviewed journals and magazines in the field of Edge-Cloud computing and the IoT, via an open science practice and making the research results accessible to both technical and non-technical audiences. Specifically, CODECO follows the *Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon Europe*³. CODECO provides open science policy to all publications developed during the project, with papers being submitted in pre-print servers and relevant data on open repositories as well as targeting the *Scimago Scientific Journal and Country Rank (SJR)* rank⁴ Q1/Q2 for journals/magazines (quarter of the journals with the highest values), and ICORE⁵ A*/A/B for conferences and workshops, as has been detailed in D21 [1]. Regular scientific publications are expected in national, European, and international journals.

Table 3 provides the list of scientific publications for M1-M18, detailing the type of publication (journal/magazine; conference/workshop); citation and the *open access (OA)* paper version uploaded in Zenodo, as well as publisher link; lead partner; ranking and number of views and downloads in the CODECO Zenodo community.

Overall, the consortium produced **sixteen** successful publications (out of a proposed total of forty papers for M36), where the majority is of top quality (Q1 SJR for all journal articles; A* for most conference/workshop papers).

In terms of **impact and visibility** the papers had an impact of over 530 views and 530 downloads, which shows a significant impact of the scientific work being developed in CODECO.

Table 3: List of the CODECO's scientific publications (M1-M18).

Type	Citation	Lead Partner	Ranking Views/Downloads
Magazine /Journal Paper	Sofia, R.C., Salomon, J., Ferlin-Reiter, S., Garcés-Erice, L., Urbanetz, P., Mueller, H., Touma, R., Espinosa, A., Contreras, L.M., Theodorou, V. and Psaromanolakis, N., 2024. A Framework for Cognitive, Decentralized Container Orchestration. <i>IEEE Access</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/11517804 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10540390	FOR	Q1 SJR 10 views, 6 downloads
	Sofia, R. C., Dykeman, D., Urbanetz, P., Galal, A., and Dushyant, D., 2023. Dynamic, Context-Aware Cross-Layer Orchestration of Containerized Applications. <i>IEEE Access</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10148573 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10225530	FOR	Q1 SJR 59 views, 42 downloads
	Nan, H., Yang, S., Li, F., Trajanovski, S., Zhu, L., Wang, Y., and X Fu, X., 2023. Leveraging deep reinforcement learning with attention mechanism for virtual network function placement and routing. <i>IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/8094655 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10029903	UGOE	Q1 SJR 60 views, 131 downloads

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

⁴ <https://www.scimagojr.com/journalrank.php>

⁵ <https://portal.core.edu.au/conf-ranks/>

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Type	Citation	Lead Partner	Ranking Views/Downloads
	Sotiris, S., Mamatas, L., and Tsaoussidis, V., 2024. A Link-Quality Anomaly Detection Framework for Software-Defined Wireless Mesh Networks. <i>IEEE Transactions on Machine Learning in Communications and Networking</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/12536518 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10499246	ATH	Not available (n/a)
	Alberto, D., Serrano, J., Jimenez, D., Contreras, L. M., and Alvarez, F., 2024. Multisite gaming streaming optimization over virtualized 5G environment using Deep Reinforcement Learning techniques. <i>Computer Networks</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/11922688 Publisher: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S138912862400166X	UPM	Q1 SJR 12 views, 9 downloads
	Liang, M., Yuan, T., Wang, W., Dai, H., Sun, L., Zheng, J., Chen, G., and Fu, X., 2024. Accelerated Neural Enhancement for Video Analytics with Video Quality Adaptation. <i>IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10838336 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10483081	UGOE	Q1 SJR 33 views, 16 downloads
in Proceedings Conference/ Workshop	Yuan, T., Chung, H., Yuan, J., and Fu, X., 2023. DACOM: Learning delay-aware communication for multi-agent reinforcement learning. In <i>Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10379130 Publisher: https://ojs.aaai.org/index.php/AAAI/article/view/26389	UGOE	ICORE A* 16 views, 14 downloads
	Yuan, T., Mi, L., Wang, W., Dai, H., and Fu, X., 2023. AccDecoder: Accelerated decoding for neural-enhanced video analytics. In <i>IEEE INFOCOM 2023-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10379249 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10228933	UGOE	ICORE A* 33 views, 18 downloads
	Biao, H., Yang, S., Kuipers, F. A., Jiao, L., and Fu, X., Eavs: Edge-assisted adaptive video streaming with fine-grained serverless pipelines. In <i>IEEE INFOCOM 2023-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/8096627 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10229102	UGOE	ICORE A* 137 views, 140 downloads
	Paraskevoulakou E., Totow Tom-Ata, J., Symvoulidis C., Kyriazis, D., 2024. Enhancing Cloud-Based Application Component Placement with AI-Driven Operations. <i>IEEE 14th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10839801 Publisher: https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10427694	UPRC	n.a. 34 views, 34 downloads
	Lin, S., Wang, W., Yuan, T., Mi, L., Dai, H., Liu, Y., and Fu, X., 2024. BiSwift: Bandwidth Orchestrator for Multi-Stream Video Analytics on Edge. <i>inProc IEEE INFOCOM 2024</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10797770 Publisher: https://infocom2024.ieee-infocom.org/program/accepted-paper-list-main-conference	UGOE	ICORE A* 47 views, 34 downloads
	Samaras, G., Mertiri, M., Xezonaki, M., Theodorou, V., Chartsias, P.K., Bozios, T., 2024. Unlocking the Path Towards AI-Native Networks with Optimized Lightweight Large Language Models. <i>IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom 2024)</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/12168011 Publisher: https://meditcom2024.ieee-meditcom.org/program/main-track	ATH	Na 2 views, 2 downloads
	Skaperas, S., Koukis, G., Kapetanidou, I.A., Mamatas, L., Tsaoussidis, V., 2024. A Pragmatical Approach to Anomaly Detection Evaluation in Edge Cloud Systems. <i>inProc IEEE Infocom, ICCN workshop</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10839900 Publisher (pre-print): https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.07717	ATH	ICORE A* 44 views, 33 downloads
	Koukis, G., Skaperas, S., Kapetanidou, I.A., Mamatas, L., Tsaoussidis, V., 2024. Performance Evaluation of Kubernetes Networking Approaches	ATH	ICORE C 7 views, 5 downloads

Type	Citation	Lead Partner	Ranking Views/Downloads
	across Constraint Edge Environments. <i>inProc ISCC 2024 (ECO 2024 workshop)</i> . Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/11919057 Publisher: https://sites.google.com/view/eco-2024		
	Koukis, G., Skaperas, S., Kapetanidou, I. A., Tsaoussidis, V., Mamatas, L., 2024. An Open-Source Experimentation Framework for the Edge Cloud Continuum. <i>inProc Infocom 2024, CNERT 2024 workshop</i> Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/10840008 Publisher: https://infocom.info/workshops/track/CNERT	ATH	ICORE A* 49 views, 51 downloads
	Samaras, G., Mertiri, M., Xezonaki, M., Theodorou, V., Chartsias P.K., Bozios, T., 2024. Democratizing Predictive Analytics with Generative Artificial Intelligence towards AI-Native Networks. <i>ECO 2024, co-located with the 29th IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)</i> Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/12518194 Publisher: https://sites.google.com/view/eco-2024	ICOM	ICORE C 3 views, 4 downloads

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of various publication types developed in CODECO over its first 18-month period, providing a global view, as CODECO has also contributed with the development of standardisation contributions, detailed in section 5.

Figure 2: Distribution of different publication types by CODECO during the period M1– M18.

4.2 Presentations

Presentations of the CODECO project are aiming at targeting specific audiences concerning the type of event, such as conferences, small talks, webinars, and workshops. They are used to provide an overview of the project, present technical details, and results, and importantly, to engage stakeholders in discussions and promote the adoption of CODECO technologies, raise awareness about its results, and foster collaboration.

Table 4 lists the achieved CODECO representation in different types of events, organized or proposed by different partners. Presentations are usually handled and discussed in CODECO and are regularly monitored in the context of WP6 and registered in an internal document by all partners. Furthermore, when presentations are delivered, they are also made available via Zenodo, under the rubric “Presentations”⁶. In the first period of CODECO, partners provided twelve direct presentations with focus on CODECO aspects.

⁶https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco/records?q=&f=resource_type%3Apresentation&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

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Table 4: CODECO achieved presentations from M1-M18.

Activity	Date	Location	Target Audience Total participants	Description	Link
AI-SPRINT final event	11.10.2023	Online (Milan, Italy)	AR, ICT, GOV Total: 70	Presentation of CODECO in Session 5: Open Source and Emerging Trend.	https://zenodo.org/records/12537728
EUCEI concertation meeting	16.05.2023	Brussels, Belgium	AR, ICT, GOV Total: 50	CODECO pitch and participation in panel by FOR, Rute C. Sofia	https://zenodo.org/records/10391200
BDVA Dataweek 2023	14.06.2023	Lulea, Sweden	AR, ICT, GOV Total: 340	Rizkallah Touma (i2CAT) presents CODECO during the session on "Building a Cognitive Cloud-Edge Continuum for Next-Generation Data Processing Applications"	https://zenodo.org/records/12663362
Nexus Forum 2023	5-6.10.2023	Brussels, Belgium	AR, ICT, EUS, GOV Total:	I2CAT, Rizkallah Touma, representing CODECO in the session "High-Impact Horizon Europe Projects,".	https://zenodo.org/records/12663398
IEEE WF-IoT	23.10.2023	Online (Aveiro, Portugal)	AR, ICT, GOV, EUS Total:	Introduction to CODECO in the context of CEI and the Energy domain, provided by FOR, Rute C. Sofia	https://zenodo.org/records/12537641
DISCOVER-US Webinars	22.03.2024	Online	AR, ICT, EUS, DEV Total: 40	Talk on CODECO aspects towards USA/EU via the CSA Discover-US by FOR, Rute C. Sofia; provide as tutorial to the EU-USA community.	https://zenodo.org/records/12657798 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CDqrUbZ
Red Hat Tech Talks	14.02.2024	Cork, Ireland	AR, ICT, EUS, DEV Total: n.a.	Introduce CODECO, overview, Red Hat work on CODECO; bring CODECO to the RedHat Kubernetes communities.	https://zenodo.org/records/12658038
EUCEI/ACES Webinars "RIA Showcase"	18.04.2024	Online	AR, ICT, EUS, DEV Total: 77	Collaborate and showcase CODECO with particular focus on AI orchestration.	https://zenodo.org/records/12657871
DevConf. CZ 2024.	13-15.06.2024	Brno, Czech Republic	AR, ICT, EUS, DEV Total: n.a.	Introduce CODECO, overview, architecture, Red Hat work on CODECO, by Ray Carrol and Alka Nixon.	https://zenodo.org/records/12657890 https://pretalx.com/devconf-cz-2024/talk/3XMWSB/
IEEE ISCC ECO 2024	26.06.2024	Paris, France	AR, ICT Total: 20	Keynote speech by FOR, Rute C. Sofia – see also organized events.	https://zenodo.org/records/12657995
IA382 FEEC - Unicamp Seminar in Computer Engineering	02.05.2024	Online (Brazil)	AR, ICT Total: 30	FOR, Rute C. Sofia presents on "Latest trends on supporting an energy-efficient and resilient IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum" and CODECO.	https://zenodo.org/records/12658016
Master seminar, University of Piraeus	06.06.2024	Piraeus, Greece	AR, ICT Total: n.a.	UPRC to lead a presentation on the CODECO framework to students from the University's Masters Programme in Big Data Analytics and Information Systems and Services.	https://zenodo.org/records/12658080

4.3 Technical Programme Committee Representation

CODECO members participate actively in relevant technical and scientific programme committees of conferences and workshops that relate with CODECO, thus extending the reach and bringing awareness to topics being discussed in the project.

Table 5: TPC representation by CODECO members in events related with CODECO technological enablers.

Activity Name	Location, date	CODECO Technological enablers	Partners
IEEE ICDCS 2023: 43rd IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems	Online (Hong Kong), 18-21.07.2023	Cloud, Edge computing AI for distributed systems Mobile and wireless computing	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – TPC member
IEEE Smart World Congress – 2023 IEEE International Conference on Metaverse	Portsmouth, UK, 28-31.08.2023	Edge-Cloud orchestration	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – TPC member
18th Workshop on Mobility in the Evolving Internet Architecture (MobiArch) 2023 – co-located with ACM Mobicom 2023	Madrid, Spain, 6.10.2023	Cloud, Edge computing Mobile networking and mobile computing	UGOE, Tingting Yuan – Chair TID, Luis Miguel Contreras Murillo – Chair (rf. to section 4.4 – organized events)
IEEE NoF 2023: International Conference on Network of the Future 2023	Izmir, Turkey, 4-6.10.2023	QoS Overlay networks. Energy efficiency in networks Edge and fog computing/networking	UGOE, Xiaoming Fu – TPC co-chair
IARIA ISCNC 2023: The Eighteenth International Conference on Systems and Networks Communications	Valencia, Spain, 13-17.11.2023	Software defined networking. Mobile networking	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – TPC member
EUCNCNC CONASENSE 2024	Antwerp, Belgium, 03.06.2024	Edge computing 6G Edge-Cloud continuum	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – Chair (rf. to section 4.4 – organized events)
IEEE ICDCS 2024: 44th IEEE International conference on distributed systems	NJ, USA, 23-26.07.2024	Cloud, Edge computing AI for distributed systems Mobile and wireless computing	UGOE, Xiaoming Fu – TPC co-chair FOR, Rute C. Sofia – TPC member
IEEE CSCN 2024: IEEE conference on Standards for Communications and Networking	25-27.11.2024, Belgrade, Serbia	Dynamic scheduling ML for networking SDN architectures and interfaces	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – TPC member
IEEE WPMC 2024: International Symposium on Wireless Personal Multimedia Communications	17-20.11.2024, Noida, India	6G Edge-Cloud continuum	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – Europe TPC chair
IEEE WPMC 2024 CONASENSE 6G-SAC workshop	19.11.2024	6G Edge-Cloud continuum Energy-efficiency in the Cloud-Edge-IoT	FOR, Rute C. Sofia – co-Chair
IEEE ISCC First International Edge-Cloud Orchestration (ECO) 2024 workshop	26.06.2024	Edge-Cloud orchestration	ATH, Vassilis Tsaoussidis – Chair FOR, Rute C. Sofia – co-chair ATH, Lefteris Mamatas – TPC chair (rf. to section 4.4 – organized events)

4.4 Events

To highlight the contributions of the CODECO project, clear and engaging presentations for high-profile events from the project's inception has been planned. This includes industrial, academic, software developer, and demonstration events.

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The participation of the CODECO team in conferences and workshops related to Edge-Cloud computing, IoT, and related fields promotes the dissemination of its research results and facilitates interaction with other experts in the field.

Some examples of relevant events for the CODECO project could include:

- International conferences on Edge-Cloud computing, IoT, and decentralized systems.
- Industry events focused on Edge-Cloud computing and the IoT.
- Workshops, tutorials, and other technical events focused on specific topics such as decentralized data management.
- Public events, such as technology or innovation conferences, panel discussions provide opportunities to engage with the public.

This section therefore covers all events where CODECO was represented from M1-M18, as listed in Table 6. The events listed comprise therefore events where presentations were delivered. This aspect is specifically indicated in the table.

Furthermore, the next sections describe in more detail the key events organized by CODECO, and the key events where CODECO was represented.

Table 6: Overview of the public events and conferences CODECO organized or participated from M1-M18.

Title	Location	Lead Partner(s)	Purpose	Date	Total Audience
EUCEI concertation meeting	Brussels, Belgium	FOR	Dissemination and networking. Rf to presentations (section 4.2)	10-11.05.2023	Over 100
EclipseCON	Ludwigsburg, Germany	ECL	Dissemination and networking	16-19.10.2023	Over 200
6G CONASENSE workshop - co-located with IEEE WPMC2023	Orlando, FL, USA	FOR	Organizer, dissemination, and networking	19.11.2023	40
WF-IoT 2023	Aveiro, Portugal	FOR	Invitation, Panel participation -The CODECO orchestration framework - value add for smart, decentralized energy environments ". Rf to presentations (section 4.2)	23.10.2023	70 (panel)
Nexus Forum 2023	Brussels, Belgium	i2CAT	Dissemination and networking Rf to presentations (section 4.2)	5-6.10.2023	Over 100
AI-SPRINT final event	Online	FOR	Dissemination and impact Rf to presentations (section 4.2)	11.10.2023	70
First CODECO Industrial Workshop – co-located with HiPEAC 2024	Munich, Germany	FOR, ECL	Inception event - first CODECO industrial workshop HiPEAC 2024 booth (ECL)	16-19.01.2024	60
Embedded World 2024	Nuremberg, Germany	ECL	Booth Impact, Dissemination, networking, community building	9-11.04.2024	Over 100

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Title	Location	Lead Partner(s)	Purpose	Date	Total Audience
DevConf.CZ	Brno, Czech Republic	RHT	Talk Impact, dissemination. Rf to presentations (section 4.2)	13-15.06.2024	Over 100
Third Eclipse SAAM Conference 2023 - co-located with EclipseCON	Ludwigsburg , Germany	ECL	Organizer	17.10.2023	Over 50
AAA12023	Washington DC	UGOE	Paper presentation (rf. to section 4.1 scientific publications)	14-15.02.2023	Over 20
MobiArch 2023	Madrid, Spain	UGOE, TID, FOR	Organizers and CODECO panel	6.10.2023	30
IEEE NoF 2023: International Conference on Network of the Future 2023	Izmir, Turkey	UGOE	Impact, dissemination Organizer	4-6.10.2023	Not available (n.a.)
The 2023 IEEE International Conference on Metaverse (Metaverse 2023)	Portsmouth, UK	FOR	Dissemination, networking, community building TPC (rf. to section 4.3)	28-31.08-2023	n.a.
IARIA ICSNC 2023 (The Eighteenth International Conference on Systems and Networks Communication s)	Valencia, Spain	FOR	TPC (rf. to section 4.3)	13-17.11.2023	n.a.
ICDCS 2023 - 43rd IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems	Hong Kong	FOR	TPC (rf. to section 4.3)	18-21.07.2023	n.a.
IEEE Smart World Congress - 2023 IEEE International Conference on Metaverse	Portsmouth, UK	FOR	TPC (rf. to section 4.3)	28-31.08.2023	n.a.
EUCNC CONASENSE 2024	Antwerpen, Belgium	FOR	Organizer Community building, dissemination	03.06.2024	60
IEEE ISCC ECO 2024	Paris. France	ATH	Organizer Scientific outreach, dissemination	26.06.2024	20

4.4.1 Organised by CODECO

4.4.1.1 IEEE ISCC: ECO 2024 Workshop

Description	URL
Event Website	https://sites.google.com/view/eco-2024
Presentations and videos (Zenodo)	https://zenodo.org/records/12657995
IEEE ISCC 2024	https://2024.ieee-iscc.org/
When/Where	26 th -29 th June 2024, Paris, France
Lead	ATH
Involved partners	FOR, ICOM, ATH, INO
Target stakeholders	AR, ICT

ECO 2024 corresponds to one of the proposed scientific events organized by CODECO and aims at strengthening the development of research in the context of a flexible Edge-Cloud continuum.

This scientific workshop aims to shed light on the aspects of orchestration that deal with fundamental challenges in the Edge-Cloud continuum such as efficient resource and network bandwidth utilization, microservices deployment, data management, adaptive and automated cross-layer configuration, anomaly detection, and security. Paradigms that concern specific use-case applications, pragmatical evaluation and experimentation, are of special interest for this workshop. We also encourage theoretical contributions, such as ML approaches for resource-constraint environments, distributed learning, and optimization.

The workshop, organized by ATH (Vassilis Tsaoussidis, Lefteris Mamatas), corresponds to a first workshop edition which has been proposed to be co-located with IEEE ISCC 2024 in Paris. The workshop received 11 paper submissions, out of which five papers have been accepted, following the rules of IEEE ISCC 2024 (40% acceptance rate). The event started with a keynote on the CODECO project provided by the project Coordinator (Rute C. Sofia), followed by a hands-on demonstration of the CODECO experimental framework by ATH (George Koukis), and then by the presentation of the accepted papers. The workshop counted with a small audience of circa 20 participants, as would be expected in a first edition.

CODECO, under its IRCEP programme, will provide financial reimbursement to the author of a paper shortlisted by the workshop's organizer.

4.4.1.2 EUCNC: CONASENSE 2024 Workshop

Description	URL
CONASENSE workshop	https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-11/
Presentations and videos	-
EUCNC 2024	https://www.eucnc.eu/
When/Where	3 rd June 2024, Antwerp, Belgium
Lead	FOR
Partners	UPM, TID, ATH, INO, INTRA
Target stakeholders	AR, ICT, GOV

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The EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 workshop focuses on the need to address such adaptation from a cross-layer perspective, where computation and networking are intertwined via. softwarization and via an AI-based knowledge plane.

The main objective of the workshop was to bring together an interdisciplinary perspective on 6G, stemming from research being developed in Europe and other continents. The workshop will be driven by the 6G CONASENSE platform⁷, with the support of the HE CODECO (cognitive continuum), HE NEMO⁸ (next generation meta-OS) and HE INSTAR⁹ (cross-country standardisation) projects.

The workshop brought together novel work across complementary 6G perspectives: **communications; satellites and navigation; sensing**; 6G use-cases and services.

The debate on 6G services and technologies, considering different domains and the use of AI to develop technological solutions by integrating human behaviour (e.g. trustworthiness, mobility) and sustainable design, brings innovation disruption and has the potential to create impact in terms of novel services, thus driving technological design towards societal advancement.

Derived from the workshop, the organizers shall edit an open access book with chapters based on the best presentations and focusing on the technological advancements and standardization. The book will be part of the CONASENSE book series, edited by River publishers, and is expected to be started in quartal 3 2024.

The workshop started with two presentations concerning perspectives on 6G in India (Dr. Vandala Rohokale, locally supported by Mr. Paulo Rufino, CTIF Global Capsule Denmark), and in Brazil, provided by Dr. Christian Esteve Rothenberg.

The second session concerned perspectives on the 6G flexible Edge-Cloud continuum. A first presentation was provided by Dr. Valerio Frasca (Intel Germany) on the context of the 6G-Senses with a particular focus on location tracking based on far Edge devices, and the integration of deterministic behaviour in the far Edge.

After the break, the projects HE-NEMO and CODECO presented several technical sessions, focusing on the key aspects being developed.

From CODECO, partner TID presented the CODECO Networking Management and Adaptation component, followed by an introduction to the CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit by partner ICOM. The CODECO session closed with a presentation on the CODECO experimentation framework by ATH.

The last session was dedicated to the recently started INSTAR project, and to the INSTAR 6G workstream.

The workshop counted with a total of 60 participants, out of which 12 were invited speakers. As follow-up, the invited speakers will be invited to develop a chapter for a book with focus on the 6G flexible Edge-Cloud orchestration.

⁷ <https://www.conasense.org/>

⁸ <https://meta-os.eu/>

⁹ <https://instarstandards.org/>

Figure 3: EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 Workshop.

4.4.1.3 HiPEAC 2024: CODECO First Industrial Workshop and Booth

Description	URL
HiPEAC workshop	https://www.hipeac.net/2024/munich/#/program/sessions/8105/
Presentations and videos	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10868462
HiPEAC 2024	https://www.hipeac.net/2024/munich/#/
When/Where	18 th January 2024, Garching (Munich), Germany
Lead	FOR
Partners	All partners participated.
Target stakeholders	AR, ICT, GOV, EUS, DEV

The first CODECO industrial workshop corresponds to the first broad event in CODECO dedicated to overall dissemination of results. The proposed format targeted SMEs, ICT, academia, and research.

The organizing committee decided to develop an organization co-located with HiPEAC as several projects focusing on cognitive computing, swarm computing and MetaOS were also represented in HiPEAC.

In Munich, the event has been organised by fortiss together with the CODECO consortium, and co-located to HiPEAC 2024, being the venue the Leibniz Supercomputer Centre (LRZ), Seminarium 1, in Garching, Germany.

The workshop had as main goal to bring awareness to the latest CODECO developments, and to be a starting point to develop the CODECO community which will be further developed in the context of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), starting from April 2024.

Specific aspects to be worked after the event in cooperation with projects in the same topics are the development of a joint white paper that has as starting point the initial discussion (panel) held with other projects during the workshop, and propose a book based on a call for chapters involving the interested attendees.

The Workshop started with an introduction by the CODECO coordinator, Rute C. Sofia, who explained the overall intention, vision of CODECO, and the status of the architecture. This session was followed by a keynote speech entitled “*From Micro to Mighty: a journey from the datacenter to the edge.*” which has been provided by the invited speaker Ricardo Noriega, RedHat.

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The technical sessions were then started, first with a session on the components of CODECO, and then followed by a session on the CODECO use-cases.

The workshop counted with a panel discussion involving the coordinators of COGNIT and COGNIFOG, focusing on challenges and opportunities in the context of Edge-Cloud orchestration. Moderated by John Soldatos, Netcompany-Intrasoft, the panel had as main objective to present to the audience three different approaches (COGNIFOG, COGNIT, CODECO) to managing heterogeneous resources and services across the cloud/edge/IoT continuum, along with characteristic use cases. For 45 minutes, the coordinators of the 3 projects introduced the projects, challenges, and next steps. Then, technological enablers and technical approach of the different projects was discussed. Finally, the panel debated on current applications and use-cases, with emphasis on their business & socio-economic benefits (e.g., cost reduction/efficiency, power/energy efficiency, enhanced privacy, new opportunities for SMEs etc.)

Figure 4: HIPEAC 2024 CODECO First Industrial Workshop.

The final session related with an overview on engagement aspects in CODECO: open-source code, experimenting with CODECO, and the CODECO IRCEP programme.

As an inception event, the workshop proposed a set of next steps to the participants, specifically:

- the joint development of a white paper on orchestration aspects, to be released in quarter three of 2024, involving other projects on the cognitive computing topic.
- A new book with focus on the 6G Edge-Cloud flexible continuum. The call for chapters will be directed to the current registered attendants, and to related projects, expected to be drafted in quarter four of 2024.
- The further development of the CODECO community via the CODECO IRCEP Programme.

In addition to the organization of the first Industrial Workshop, partner Eclipse had a booth at the main hall from 16th to 19th January 2024, where the open-source foundation explained the CODECO project and the CODECO Toolkit main functionalities to around 700 visitors which attended the event. The next pictures show the booth where the CODECO project was displayed and some of the attendees interested in the project.

Figure 5: CODECO at the Eclipse Foundation booth during HiPEAC 2024.

4.4.1.4 ACM Mobicom: MobiArch 2023 Workshop

Description	URL
ACM MobiArch Workshop 2023	https://mobiarch2023.github.io/
Presentations and videos	Na
Mobicom 2023	https://www.sigmobile.org/mobicom/2023/
When/Where	6 th October 2023, Madrid, Spain
Lead	UGOE
Partners	TID, FOR, SIE
Target stakeholders	AR, ICT

The 2023 *Workshop on Mobility in the Evolving Internet Architecture (MobiArch)* was held in conjunction with ACM MobiCom 2023. in Madrid, Spain, 6th October 2023.

ACM MobiCom stands as a distinguished event that attracts a multitude of experts from the target stakeholder groups AR and ICT. Such event enriches the discourse and bolsters CODECO towards the scientific community of excellence.

The *MobiArch 2023* workshop acts as an interactive platform, bringing together experts and thought leaders to explore the latest research trends and prospective developments in the realm of mobile communications and mobile Internet infrastructures. It delved into critical system and radio access challenges that must be addressed to realize reliable, high-performance, and scalable mobile networking systems. With the support of the CODECO project, this event delved deeply into the burgeoning field of Cognitive Decentralized Edge Cloud Orchestration. Participants engaged in in-depth discussions, exchange knowledge, and provide industry-focused insights on how these advanced technologies are shaping the future of mobile networking.

The *MobiArch 2023* workshop was planned to span the entire day and comprised two keynotes, two technical sessions featuring presentations of six papers, and a panel session supported by the CODECO project.

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It counted with circa 30 attendees, including speakers (circa 8). This gathering served as a platform for assessing the relevance, for the audience, of the Cognitive Edge-Cloud Continuum problem space, showcasing the impact and implications that our research can have on the state-of-the-art solutions. The presentation of six papers not only highlighted the timely value proposition of the project objectives, but also ignited discussions on crucial issues within our field.

The CODECO project has also organized a discussion panel at Mobiarch 2023 entitled “The Edge-Cloud Continuum, Flexible Orchestration Challenges and Drivers. The panel, moderated by Rute C. Sofia, Coordinator, (FOR), focused on the challenges and drivers for the Edge-Cloud continuum, featuring insights from experts from Yale University, (USA), Telefonica (Spain), and Siemens AG (Germany). The moderator introduced the speakers and the CODECO project and it followed by 10-minute talks from each speaker. There was a Q&A session where the audience can engage with the speakers and the moderator. The questions and comments received from the audience were also a valuable input for the project. The session concluded with a summary of the main discussion points.

4.4.2 Participation in External Events

4.4.2.1 Embedded World 2024

CODECO was present at Embedded World 2024, which took place in Nuremberg from the 9th to the 11th of April 2024. The Eclipse Foundation had a booth at the Hall 4 in the event, where the CODECO project could be disseminated to the attendees. More than 32.000 visitors attended this event, where there were interesting discussions about the project and the potential benefits of the open-source results of the project.

Figure 6: CODECO at the Eclipse Foundation booth in Embedded World 2024.

4.4.2.2 EUCEI ACES RIA Showcase 2024

CODECO participated in the EUCEI ACES RIA Show-case Webinar entitled “*Future proof solutions for cognitive enabled cloud computing*”¹⁰. The Webinar took place on April 18th, 2024, from 10.30-13.00 CET, online, being organized by EUCEI and ACES. The event recording is available online¹¹. The event has been introduced by Albert Seubers, the Open Continuum Coordinator, and chaired by Fred Buining, the technical coordinator of the ACES-EDGE project. Seven projects on the cognitive computing topic actively participated in the presentations and the discussions: seven projects: CODECO by Rute Sofia; EDGELESS by Claudio Cicconetti; ENACT by Alexandros Nizamis; INTEND by Hui Song; CoGNET by Georgios Spanos; COGNIT by Marco Mancini; and CLOUDSKIN by Marc Sanchez Artigas. The event counted with an audience of about 77 attendees. The Webinar report provides the main findings¹²:

- There are immense values in the diversity of the technologies developed in the Cloud-Edge continuum. The Edge-Cloud is the first hop from the device onto the web.
- Developing a cloud that runs at the first hop and that is powerful enough to process big data and AI locally, will be an enabler for digital sovereignty and could be developed by European Entities and allows the enforcement of European values on applications, data sharing and AI.
- AI requires datasets for training and there is an enormous potential in public sector information. Furthermore, another challenge is to develop models to monetize these datasets.

Values emerging:

- a clear trend towards technologically complex and ambitious projects, however the concrete application of such complexity is a bit risky, even if the high challenges have potential.
- lots of touchpoints between the projects and different angles to tackle different types of problems and to find multifaceted solutions.
- data is fluent, and the actual processes, the values, and the benefits almost in all cases occur at the Edge.
- the interest in the potential in LLMs.
- the development of common tools and solutions, pursuing common targets with different approaches.
- All these developments would benefit from the development and availability of large-scale testbeds and large-scale infrastructures.

¹⁰ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/webinar-report-future-proof-solutions-for-cognition-enabled-cloud-computing>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2sMNsANdBvg>

¹² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/webinar-report-future-proof-solutions-for-cognition-enabled-cloud-computing/>

Figure 7: CODECO participation in EUCEI ACES RIA show-case Webinar.

4.4.2.3 EclipseCON 2023

EclipseCON stands as the premier conference gathering developers, architects, and open-source business leaders to delve into Eclipse technologies, exchange best practices, and collaborate. It represents CODECO's flagship annual event, uniting the Eclipse ecosystem with industry leaders to tackle shared challenges and drive innovation in open-source runtimes, tools, and frameworks. Discussions span cloud and edge applications, IoT, artificial intelligence, connected vehicles, digital ledger technologies, and beyond. last year, EclipseCON¹³ has been hold 16th - 19th October 2023 in Ludwigsburg, Germany, which has over 460 participants.

4.4.2.4 WF-IoT 2023

The 9th IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things¹⁴ took place in Aveiro, Portugal at the Aveiro Congress Centre from 12th to 27th October 2023. IEEE WF-IoT2023 brought together experts from IoT-Edge-Cloud.

HE-CODECO, represented by its Coordinator Rute C. Sofia, participated in the vertical panel 5 "Energy, Power, and Sustainability" on 23rd October at 15.00, online. The presentation provided focused on an explanation of the novel CODECO orchestration framework and its role as a decentralized, cognitive container orchestration in the context of smart, decentralized energy environments. The talk was also focused on how energy stakeholder groups can test and apply the open-source CODECO framework to novel use-cases, to assist in an optimized of the energy demand, supply, storage, across multi-tenant domains.

4.4.2.5 AI-SPRINT Final Event 2023

Led by Politecnico di Milano, the AI-SPRINT Final Event: "Unveiling the transformative potential of AI-SPRINT" introduced cutting-edge AI tools and featured insights from global analysts. AI-SPRINT is an EU-funded project dedicated to defining a novel framework for the design and operation of AI applications in computing continuum.

¹³ <https://www.eclipsecon.org/2023>

¹⁴ <https://wfio2023.iot.ieee.org/>

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CODECO, represented by its Coordinator participated in the session “Open Source and Emerging Trends”, show-casing CODECO as an OSS (Open-Source Software)-oriented project. The presentation¹⁵ explained the agile methodology around CODECO’s components’ design and methodology, to allow for the development of a successful OSS ecosystem that supports AI-based orchestration across the Edge-Cloud continuum.

4.4.2.6 Nexus Forum

NexusForum 2023¹⁶, the inaugural event organized by Open Nebula, brought together key players to explore the synergies between the European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge, and Cloud, EU institutions, and member countries. This landmark occasion highlighted the endeavours of three Horizon Europe projects managed by HADEA, aiming to drive digital transformation in Europe. One of the standout projects was CODECO, represented by partner I2CAT (Dr. Rizkallah Touma).

I2CAT provided a presentation of CODECO with a particular focus on the work in the domains of context-awareness and decentralized intelligence.

4.4.2.7 EUCEI First Concertation Meeting

The CODECO Project participated on the EUCEI event Concertation and Consultation in May 2023 as one of the flagship projects on “Cognitive Cloud”, represented by its Coordinator, Rute C. Sofia (FOR).

The project participated with a pitch¹⁷ highlighting key assets of CODECO and has also participated on the Hub4Cloud panel “Resource orchestration and adaptation in the continuum”, moderated by Giovanni Rimassa (Hub4Cloud Coordinator – CIO Martel Innovate). The panel counted with the following speakers: Manos Varvarigos, Coordinator of SERRANO; Fulvio Risso, Coordinator of FluidOS; Rute C. Sofia Coordinator of CODECO. The panel focused on the main challenges concerning an adaptive and cognitive continuum, envisioning next-generation IoT applications.

4.5 Engagement and Awareness Activities

CODECO's current communication, dissemination, and promotion efforts include a variety of engagement and awareness activities designed to connect with the audience effectively. These activities feature innovative formats such as podcasts, videocasts, and short interviews. CODECO partners are participating by answering specific questions, either suggested by the audience or pre-determined, about the project or related AI topics. CODECO present in LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/codeco-project/>) and X (formerly Twitter) (<https://x.com/CodecoProject>).

Webinars and online workshops are being organized to inform and engage the public, stakeholders, and media about the project's progress and outcomes. YouTube videos, hosted on the existing FOR YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@fortissTV/playlists>) or a new dedicated channel, along with other multimedia content, are being created to make the research more accessible to a wider audience. These videos are posted on the project's website and shared on social media platforms.

The CODECO team is actively attending and participating in panel discussions or interactive sessions at relevant meetings and events, to further engage with attendees and present their research results.

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/12537728>

¹⁶ <https://opennebula.io/innovation/nexusforum2023/>

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/10391200>

4.6 Collaborative Actions and Synergies

The CODECO project aims to collaborate with industry partners and academic institutions to promote research results and develop new technologies and applications. It seeks to establish close cooperation with relevant NGI, Cloud, and broader ICT initiatives, as well as standards groups like IETF/IRTF and open-source initiatives such as the Linux Cloud Foundation. These collaborations provide access to new ideas, technologies, and resources, fostering knowledge exchange and cross-learning. The project intends to continue these collaborations in future projects, forming new consortiums for ongoing research.

In this context, collaborative actions have been developed towards other projects and associations as mentioned next.

4.6.1 EUCEI

A first set of actions has been established in EUCEI, initiative which seeks to establish a pathway for comprehending and advancing the Cloud, Edge, and IoT (CEI) Continuum. It aims to foster collaboration among diverse research projects, developers, suppliers, business users, and potential adopters of this innovative technological paradigm. The monitoring and contributions towards different EUCEI taskforces are being handled under WP6, T6.3 (Standardisation), coordinated by FOR. Table 7 summarizes the contributions and monitoring of CODECO to EUCEI.

Table 7: Contributions and monitoring of CODECO to EUCEI.

TF nr	Partners involved	Purpose	Main achievements
1- Strategic Liaisons	FOR, INO	Engagement of SDOs; Management of interactions with AIOTI/ECS/GAIA-X/etc.; standardisation and interoperability approaches, led by the Inside Industry Association	Monitoring
2- OSS engagement strategies	ECL (leader)	Successfully OSS launch; methodologies	CODECO OSS guidelines aligned with EUCEI
3- Architecture	ATOS (lead); FOR	taxonomy definitions; sharing of components between RIAs; creation of a common reference architecture (IoT-Edge_Cloud continuum); peer reviewing and testing	Contributions to the architecture; to white papers and use-case catalogues
4- Ecosystem engagement	INO, FOR	open calls, definition of commercial pilots, commercial relationships, and workshops	Alignment of the IRCEP programme
5- Market and sectors	INTRA	Use-cases characterization; definition of relevant value-chains; commercialization support	Not applicable (WP7, not active)
6- Communications	INO	Overall dissemination and communication	Engagement in different events (Rf. to section 3); contributions to white papers

4.6.2 Collaboration with other projects

CODECO has established, based on its activities, a set of engagement and collaboration activities with projects on the same topic, or related topics. A list of the established activities are as follows:

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- HE COGNIFOG¹⁸ expects to reuse components of CODECO, namely, its scheduler (*Seamless Workload Migration, SWM*) and its AI-based orchestrator (*Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning, PDLC*).
- CODECO is creating a white paper focused on different approaches to Edge-Cloud orchestration, involving all projects related with the topic (e.g., COGNIT¹⁹, COGNIFOG, DECICE²⁰, EDGELESS²¹). The white paper derives from the CODECO First Industrial Workshop and will be released in quartal 4 2024.
- CODECO and HE-NEMO have agreed, in EUCNC CONASENSE2024, to develop a joint workshop to explore the possibility to reuse/align the semantic networking composition aspects across the two projects.
- CODECO is developing a book derived from the talks presented in EUCNC CONASENSE2024, with focus on different approaches to the 6G flexible Edge-Cloud continuum challenges.

5 Standardisation in CODECO

Standardisation activities in CODECO are handled within the context of T6.3 which started in M10. During the initial development of T6.3 (M10, October 2023, until M15, March 2024), the task developed an initial standardisation plan, detailing proposed initial contributions to specific *Standards Development Organisations (SDOs)*, but also with pre-standardisation entities and with open-source alliances and consortia, relevant to the uptake of the CODECO ecosystem. Of particular focus are *European SDOs (EDOs)* such as ETSI and related association/consortia such as AIOTI, with focus on Edge-Cloud flexibilization, and international SDOs such as IEEE, IETF, covering relevant aspects of orchestration, e.g., network exposure, network and computational management based on AI.

For the sake of simplification, during the next section the term SDO shall be used to reflect SDOs/EDOs, pre-normative and related association/consortia.

In this standardisation plan, sessions in related events or specific workshops with a focus on standardisation contributions are expected to be organised by the consortium.

The standardisation plan proposed between M10-M14 is detailed in section 5.1. The work in terms of monitoring and contributions developed until M18 (June 2024) is detailed in section 5.2. Future planning for the next steps is presented in section 7.3.

5.1 CODECO Standardisation Strategy and Plan

5.1.1 Strategy

The CODECO consortium and the nature of the CODECO software brings in the possibility to explore liaisons towards different SDOs, with a particular focus in open standards.

The standardisation activities in CODECO relate with the project outcome and its potential contributions to standardisation and policy-making activities. It also relates with an identification (and contribution to) relevant existing standards and relevant policies that may impact the development of the CODECO project. For this, CODECO standardisation strategy considers a three-phase approach, illustrated in Figure 8 and described next:

¹⁸ <https://cognifog.eu>

¹⁹ <https://cognit.sovereignedge.eu/>

²⁰ <https://www.decice.eu/>

²¹ <https://edgeless-project.eu/>

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- **Setup (M1-M15):**
 - Initial analysis of relevant SDOs to liaise with, and where CODECO can provide a meaningful contribution within its lifetime.
 - Initial research on existing standards and relevant policies, provided as a synthesized list that the consortium can check.
- **Periodic monitoring (M15-M36).** (discussed every month, WP6 regular meetings) of relevant developments in the identified SDOs, based on the monitoring and involvement in SDOs provided by assigned partners.
- **Periodic Contributions (M18-M36).** Periodic analysis and discussion of potential contributions to SDOs, and assignment of responsibilities (discussed every four months during the CODECO plenary meetings).

Figure 8: Standardisation activities in CODECO, timeline with main phases and main expected outcome.

The expected outcome of the standardisation activities in CODECO are expected in the following categories of indicators:

- **White papers**, providing alignment, vision, and recommendations concerning specific European policies and SDOs.
- **Reference architectures and taxonomies.** Derived from the developments of CODECO, contributions are expected to SDOs and SDO-related entities developing efforts to create Cloud-Edge-IoT reference architectures and taxonomies (e.g., AIOTI, EUCEI), or to align with reference CEI architectures (e.g., ETSI, IETF)
- **Standardisation-oriented meetings.** Based on specific contributions or findings, the consortium expects to contribute to standardization meetings eventually involving other projects, and SDOs.

5.1.2 Plan

While the CODECO integrates a good balance between academic and industrial partners, and while all industry partners are involved in the standardization activities, standardization is a complex process which requires a significant level of commitment by the involved partners.

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Due to this, an initial plan has been built based on the following aspects, and steps taken in the first 18 months are summarised in Table 8, and described next:

- **WHAT:** which topics and assets of CODECO may have standardization potential; and which form can contributions be provided.
- **WHERE:** which SDOs, pre-standardisation entities, related consortia and associations are relevant to CODECO and can be considered for specific assets.
- **HOW:** how to best achieve relevant contributions.
- **WHO:** from the consortium, who can lead and support standardisation activities and efforts.
- **WHEN:** how to be able to detect as soon as possible when contributions need to be provided, in alignment with the SDOs charters, roadmaps, and needs.

Table 8: CODECO initial standardisation plan, and steps taken in the first 18 months.

Step	Aspect	Actions	Status M18
WHAT	Identify standardization assets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of key assets for standardisation 	Initial list (to be revised every quartal)
	Identify relevant SDOs, entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of entities where partners can liaise and contribute meaningfully 	Achieved
	Standards in the CODECO framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of current standards and proposal for improvements (interoperability) based on derivatives, or new standards 	Planned, M18-M24.
	Gaps and contributions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of gaps and potential contributions 	M15-, periodically (every quartal, plenary meetings)
WHERE	Identification of key SDOs and related entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and monitor relevant SDOs 	Achieved
HOW	Analyse evolution of the identified groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse SDO/group roadmaps, charters and check potential gaps 	Ongoing, M15-
	Periodic monitoring and analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check evolutions of groups periodically • Update list of relevant standards • Discuss with partners 	Ongoing, M15- (every quartal)
WHO	Define individual partner activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Request partners for specific interests. • Discuss initial perspective on activities. • Assign asset leadership and potential checks on roadmaps 	Achieved, M15
	Engage with related entities that may have a strengthening impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage via related CSAs and activities (EUCEI, AIOTI, INSTAR) on related CEI standardisation initiatives 	Ongoing, M10-

5.1.2.1 WHAT

5.1.2.1.1 Identified Assets

Derived from the categories of CODECO assets, an initial identification of specific assets with relevancy to standardisation has been identified as presented in Table 9.

Table 9: List of CODECO assets with initial identified aspects that can have potential for standardisation.

Id	CODECO Asset	Identified aspects relevant for standardisation	Relevant SDOs
A1	Open, cognitive toolkits integrating the elastic and advanced concepts to manage, in a smart and flexible way, containerized applications across CEI	A1.1: ACM component, semantic definition of an application (CODECO Application Model).	IETF ²² , ETSI ²³ Open Container Initiative (OSI) ²⁴
		A1.2: NetMA and MDM components, semantic network composition model (for multi-cluster operation).	IETF, Gaia-X ²⁵
		A1.3: data-compute-network architectural approach	EUCEI, ETSI, IETF, AIOTI
		A1.4: automated management of containers in 5G	5GPPP NetWorld-Europe ²⁶
		A1.5: Secure connectivity, SDN-K8s	ETSI
		A1.6: AI approaches, trustworthiness	BDVA
		A1.7: taxonomy and definitions	EUCEI, AIOTI
A2	CODECO OSS code and repository	-	-
A3	Training tools, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework	-	-
A4	Use-cases across 4 domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Smart Buildings)	A4.1: Data sets for different domains	BDVA/DAIRO AIOTI
		A4.2: AI-based use-case profile (integration of different datasets, interoperability)	ETSI, CEN-CENELEC
		A4.3: use-cases	IETF, ETSI, AIOTI, EUCEI
A5	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme	-	-
A6	CODECO experimental infrastructure	Integration into large-scale experimentation, interoperability, multi-cluster design, scalability, resilience aspects	IETF, AIOTI

²² <https://www.ietf.org/>

²³ <https://www.etsi.org/>

²⁴ <https://opencontainers.org/>

²⁵ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

²⁶ <https://www.networldeurope.eu>

5.1.2.1.2 Relevant Policies to Align With

An initial identification of relevant policies to be monitored in the project both during the design, implementation, and runtime of CODECO as an orchestration framework is provided next. This identification was based on i) analysis of work developed in WP2 and WP3; ii) input by partners; documents provided by the CSAs supporting the DATA-01-02 topic:

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**²⁷: Privacy and data protection, privacy by design MUST be considered in CODECO as a European orchestration framework. GDPR principles are considered not only in the overall outcome (e.g., data management); it is also considered in the design of CODECO, based on the notion of **compliance** (one of the orchestration attributes considered in CODECO for application deployment). For specific data management, right to be forgotten and other GDPR provisions please refer to D3 (Data management), monitored and handled in the context of WP1, T1.1.
- **General Regulation on Data Governance Act (DGA)**²⁸. Focus on the case of CODECO is on privacy preservation aspects, and data protection in the context of use-cases. The CODECO data sets will be publicly available via the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab repository²⁹ and as such specific handling in alignment with the DGA MUST be observed. These aspects are articulated in WP1 (T1.1) and WP5 (T5.1).
- **EU Cybersecurity Act (CSA)**³⁰: CSA introduces a harmonized European system for the cybersecurity certification of ICT products, services, and processes. The main objective of the Cybersecurity Act (CSA) is to improve protection against threats to cybersecurity within the EU. CODECO MUST consider the latest developments of the EU Cybersecurity act³¹ The NIS2 Directive provides legal measures to establish a higher level of cybersecurity and resilience within organizations of the European Union. This directive affects AI4Gov during the project life.
- **EU Cyber Resilient (CRA) act**³²: CODECO SHOULD consider the CRA in the context of OSS code development and CRA code criticality levels. This monitoring and analysis will be done in the context of WP5, T5.1, concerning the CODECO OSS framework, smart apps, and experimentation tools developed in the project, such as the CODECO data generator.
- **EU NIS2 directive**³³: NIS2 aims to improve the cybersecurity of essential services for organisations that have business operations located in the EU. CODECO as an orchestration framework SHOULD observe the reservations towards K8s due to the use of containerization. The CODECO framework images and dependencies are secure and that there are robust security controls and incident reporting measures is essential to counter these threats effectively. These aspects are monitored in the context of WP5, T5.1 and must be handled in the technical WPs developing CODECO (WP3, WP4).
- **EU AI Act (AIA)**: CODECO NEEDS to monitor the latest developments of the AIA and ensure alignment in terms of AI governance and resilience. This aspect is monitored in the context of T5.1 and handled in WP3, WP4.

5.1.2.2 WHERE

Based on the initial identification of contributions, expertise of partners in the consortium and liaisons, the following SDOs have been considered as initial targets to monitor, to follow the development of groups and standards, and to contribute to.

²⁷ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

²⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868>

²⁹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets>

³⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

³¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

³² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cyber-resilience-act>

³³ <https://www.nis-2-directive.com/>

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Table 10: Initial identification of contributions to SDOs, with responsible partners and identified liaison topics to start with.

SDO	Description	Partners	Identified liaison topics
Big Data Value Association (BDVA) ³⁴	As an industry-driven association, BDVA focuses on all related areas of Big Data and AI technologies, such as infrastructures, data platforms, data spaces, data privacy, Industrial AI, business models, standardisation, skills, high performance computing.	UPRC, ATOS, INTRA, I2CAT	A1.6, A4.1: Contributions to CODECO on AI engineering and trustworthiness aspects in data spaces
European Committee for Standardization - European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CEN-CENELEC) ³⁵ .	CEN-CENELEC is a provider of European Standards and technical specifications.	I2CAT	A4.2: Contributions are also envisioned to CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 on AI <i>PDLC</i>
ISO (International Organization for Standardization) ³⁶ .	Is an independent, non-governmental international organization that develops and publishes international standards		
European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) ³⁷ .	provides members with an open, inclusive, and collaborative environment. This environment supports the timely development, ratification and testing of globally applicable standards for ICT-enabled systems, applications, and services	ICOM, TID, UC3M, RHT	A1.1, A1.3, A1.5, A4.2, A4.3: - Contributions in the context of Cloud/Edge application of CODECO. <i>ACM, NetMA</i> -Contributions in intent-based Edge Service Management for resource and energy efficiency. <i>PDLC, NetMA</i> -Contributions in secure connectivity, <i>NetMA</i>
Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) ³⁸ .	The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), founded in 1986, is the premier standards development organization (SDO) for the Internet. The IETF makes voluntary standards that are often adopted by Internet users, network operators, and equipment vendors, and it thus helps shape the trajectory of the development of the Internet. But in no way does the IETF control, or even patrol, the Internet.	TID, FOR	A1.3, A1.4, A4.3: - CODECO application-network integration contributions to existing RFCs CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge services - CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge computing services. <i>NetMA; use-case requirements.</i>
Pre-standardisation			
Internet Research Task Force (IRTF) ³⁹	The IRTF focuses on longer term research issues related to the Internet and is a sister organization of the IETF. It is organized into focused and long-term Research Groups that work on topics related to Internet protocols, applications, architecture, and	FOR, ATH	A6.1: - Integrate the CODECO findings about fields such as networking management; IoT; decentralised Internet services - DINRG

³⁴ <https://bdva.eu/>

³⁵ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

³⁶ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

³⁷ <https://www.etsi.org>

³⁸ <https://www.ietf.org>

³⁹ <https://www.irtf.org/>

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SDO	Description	Partners	Identified liaison topics
	technology. Research Groups have the stable long-term membership needed to promote the development of research collaboration and teamwork in exploring research issues. Participation is by individual contributors, rather than by representatives of organizations.		<i>All components, experimentation</i>
5GPPP NetWorld-Europe ⁴⁰	NetWorldEurope is the new incorporation of the European Technology Platform (ETP) for communications networks and services, the follow-up of NetWorld2020 to follow the European changing policies as stated in Horizon Europe . Communications networks and services enable interaction between users of various types of equipment, either mobile or fixed, to fulfil society's requirements for interconnection. They are the foundation of the Internet and of our digital society	FOR, I2CAT, ATOS, TID	A1.7: Integrate the CODECO ideas and the role of an automated management of containers in 5G interoperability support for Edge computing. <i>ACM</i>
Consortia and Associations			
Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI) ⁴¹ .	AIOTI supports the development of the European policies, regulation, strategies, and standardisation by providing examples, best practices, use cases and testbeds.	FOR, ICOM	A1.7, A4.1, A4.3: - Raise awareness to the role of CODECO in the context of Smart Cities; integrate the cross-layer CODECO perspective on data management, computation, and networking. - CODECO use-cases and EdgeNet interconnections as a reference testbed, aligned with the AIOTI testbed methodology. <i>All components, use-case customization.</i>
EUCEI ⁴² .	The EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT (CEI) Continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm.	FOR, ATOS, ECL	A1.3, A1.7: Architecture, taxonomy, contributions to specific standards, white papers
Gaia-X ⁴³ .	The Gaia-X initiative focuses on data sovereignty and aims to establish a sovereign and trustworthy ecosystem where data is shared. The main outcome of Gaia-X is the design of a federated system linking several Edge-Cloud service providers and users in a	FOR	A1.2: Contributions to network service composition models, based on the CODECO learnings; NetMA; MDM

⁴⁰ <https://www.networldeurope.eu>

⁴¹ <https://aioti.eu/>

⁴² <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

⁴³ <https://gaia-x.eu>

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SDO	Description	Partners	Identified liaison topics
	transparent environment across Europe.		

5.1.2.3 HOW

CODECO will follow the steps described in section 5.1.1. Monitoring will be performed via input requested to partners and discussed in WP6 meetings, and plenary meetings. Partners will be regularly requested to provide input on the status of specific contributions via surveys proposed by the task leader, FOR (M19-M36). All documentation will be made available in the CODECO repository to all partners.

Adjustments to the proposed processes are envisioned to be discussed every quartal starting from M18, in the CODECO plenary meetings. Furthermore, adjustments to the SDOs to liaise with are expected to occur regularly. Critical analysis of existing contributions is developed internally every year (M12, M24, M36) and documented in this deliverable (D18) and its subsequent deliverable (D23, M36).

5.1.2.4 WHO

The project counts with a specific taskforce for standardisation led by FOR (T6.3 leader and Coordinator) and including all industrial partners, and FOR and ATH as research partners that engage regularly in research to standardisation actions. This taskforce comprises: FOR, ATOS, ICOM, ATH, SIE, INTRA, ECL, TID, RHT, ALM. The taskforce is responsible for the overall monitoring and coordination of contributions to different SDOs. Additionally, individual partners outside the established taskforce may propose contributions, which will be aligned by the identified partner.

5.2 Contributions and Monitoring from M10-M18

Based on the proposed plan and identified liaison topics, the CODECO standardisation taskforce has been already developing contributions, despite the initial status of development of the project, in terms of standardisation potential. The status of contributions until M18 is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Contributions by partners to SDOs during M10-M18.

SDO	Partners	Identified liaison topics	Status M18
Big Data Value Association (BDVA)⁴⁴	UPRC, ATOS, INTRA, I2CAT	A1.6, A4.1: Contributions to CODECO on AI engineering and trustworthiness aspects in data spaces	<i>No contributions registered</i>
European Committee for Standardization - European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CEN-CENELEC)⁴⁵.	I2CAT	A4.2: Contributions are also envisioned to CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 on AI <i>PDLC</i>	<i>No contributions registered</i>
ISO (International Organization for Standardization)⁴⁶.			<i>No contributions registered</i>
European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)⁴⁷.	ICOM, TID/UC3M, UC3M	A1.1, A1.3, A1.5, A4.2, A4.3: Contributions in the context of Cloud/Edge application of CODECO. <i>ACM, NetMA</i>	ETSI CSC: ICOM, Contributions in the context of Cloud/Edge application of CODECO. <i>ACM, NetMA</i> to white papers. ETSI OSM: TID/UC3M, Presentation on Connectivity among VNFs using SDN.

⁴⁴ <https://bdva.eu/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.cencenelec.eu/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

⁴⁷ <https://www.etsi.org>

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SDO	Partners	Identified liaison topics	Status M18
		-Contributions in intent-based Edge Service Management for resource and energy efficiency. <i>PDLC, NetMA</i> -Contributions in secure connectivity. <i>NetMA</i>	Feature 10921 Data Plane in Kubernetes – Nov 2023 ETSI NFV: TID/UC3M, L2S-M presentation, ETSI NFV Network Operator Council (meeting #195) – June 2023
Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) ⁴⁸ .	TID/UC3M, FOR	A1.3, A1.4, A4.3: - CODECO application-network integration contributions to existing RFCs CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge services - CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge computing services. <i>NetMA; use-case requirements.</i>	IETF COINRG: TID, An Evolution of Cooperating Layered Architecture for SDN (CLAS) for Compute and Data Awareness, draft-contreras-coinrg-clas-evolution-02, Oct 2023 ⁴⁹ IETF DetNet: FOR, Requirements for Reliable Wireless Industrial Services, draft-ietf-detnet-raw-industrial-req-00, Jan 2024 ⁵⁰
Internet Research Task Force (IRTF) ⁵¹	FOR, ATH	A6.1: - Integrate the CODECO findings about fields such as networking management; IoT; decentralised Internet services - DINRG <i>All components, experimentation</i>	<i>No contributions registered</i>
5GPPP NetWorld-Europe ⁵²	FOR, I2CAT, ATOS, TID	A1.7: Integrate the CODECO ideas and the role of an automated management of containers in 5G interoperability support for Edge computing. <i>ACM</i>	Contributions to the Strategic Research Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2024: softwarization (FOR) and networking architectures (FOR; TID); Satellite Communications/Edge (FOR)
Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing (AIOTI) ⁵³ .	FOR, ICOM	A1.7, A4.1, A4.3: - Raise awareness to the role of CODECO in the context of Smart Cities; integrate the cross-layer CODECO perspective on data management, computation, and networking. - CODECO use-cases and EdgeNet interconnections as a reference testbed, aligned with the AIOTI testbed methodology. <i>All components, use-case customization.</i>	FOR, Contributions to white papers (use-cases, B5G) ⁵⁴
EUCEI ⁵⁵ .	FOR, ATOS, ECL	A1.3, A1.7: Architecture, taxonomy, contributions to specific standards, white papers	- Contributions to the overall architecture (white paper) - Use-cases (white paper) - Webinars
Gaia-X ⁵⁶ .	FOR	A1.2: Contributions to network service composition models, based on the CODECO learnings; NetMA; MDM	FOR, monitoring the Sub-WG Interconnection and networking regarding Edge-Cloud interconnection aspects.

⁴⁸ <https://www.ietf.org>

⁴⁹ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-contreras-coinrg-clas-evolution>

⁵⁰ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-detnet-raw-industrial-req/>

⁵¹ <https://www.irtf.org/>

⁵² <https://www.networldeurope.eu>

⁵³ <https://aioti.eu/>

⁵⁴ Contributions to white papers (use-cases, B5G).

⁵⁵ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

⁵⁶ <https://gaia-x.eu>

6 Impact Measurement - Summary

This section summarizes from a quantitative perspective the achieved KPIs in CODECO, against the proposed KPIs. Table 12 covers KPIs related with communication activities, while Table 13 provides KPIs concerning the scientific outreach. The KPIs were provided in the CODECO Grant Agreement and described in D21. In Table 13, only the KPIs that concern the first period of reporting are listed.

Overall, CODECO is progressing well, often exceeding the planned quantitative KPIs, e.g., as in the case of the project website, social networks, and organized events. Qualitatively, the project is also developing well, based on the developed collaborative actions, which show interest and active engagement of other projects and external partners.

Table 12: CODECO KPI reporting M1-M18.

Action	Target stakeholders	Aim	KPI (M36)	Lead	Status M18
Project Brochure	All	Disseminate the project broadly	>100 per year	FOR	1 flyer, 3 brochure(s), roll-up, poster, presentations, reach over 100 (based on events, social media).
Project Website	All	Dissemination and aggregator of all results	>500 visitors per year	FOR, INO, UGOE	826 visitors (January – June 2024)
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users	All	ECL - over 250000 subscribers ⁵⁷ . RHT - : reach to 500 viewers ⁵⁸ . EclipseFDN - :116 views ⁵⁹ FOR - over 400 viewers ⁶⁰ .
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination about the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, public magazines, and journals	1 per year	All	CODECO YouTube playlist: over 100 views Zenodo presentations: 275 views Zenodo papers: 700 views Zenodo deliverables: 901 views (D9, most viewed deliverable).
Social networks	All	Dissemination and interaction with the target stakeholders	> 200 followers on Twitter and LinkedIn	INO	Social networks: 483 followers in LinkedIn. 123 in Twitter
Industrial Event	ICT, DEV, AR, GOV, SDO, EUS	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	FOR	60 registrations

⁵⁷<https://newsroom.eclipse.org/eclipse-newsletter/2023/july/codeco-supporting-edge-cloud-continuum-open-cognitive-decentralized/>

⁵⁸ <https://research.redhat.com/blog/2024/04/03/edge-and-cloud-computing-conference-spotlights-codeco-decentralized-edge-cloud-orchestration/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.eclipse.org/research/projects/codeco/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.fortiss.org/en/research/projects/detail/codeco>

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Action	Target stakeholders	Aim	KPI (M36)	Lead	Status M18
Development events	AR, ICT, GOV, SDO	Two scientific events, a Dagstuhl seminar (UGOE) and scientific workshop (ATH) co-located with a top conference from ACM/IEEE/IFIP communities, both to be organized between year 2 and 3.	>50 participants	ATH, UGOE	1 scientific event organized (ECO2024), 20 participants
Scientific publications	AR, ICT, SDO, DEV	Regular submission of results in national, European, and international venues ¹ . CODECO shall target top venues, in particular IEEE, ACM and IFIP. CODECO shall also target European targets, such as EuCNC, CONASENSE. Publications will be made in open-science form, with papers being submitted in pre-print servers and relevant data on open repositories.	>40 peer-review, open access scientific papers	All	Over 700 views in Zenodo 16 Publications
Representation in external events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	Regularly disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific.	>50 events	All	27 events
Representation in Committees	AR, ICT	CODECO will actively participate in conferences closely related to CODECO across ACM, IEEE, IFIP. Several of the consortium members have been continuous contributors to these conference series, including as general-, program-, workshops.	>20 committees per year.	All partners	14 committees
Demonstrations	All	Project partners will also actively participate in demo sessions held at major conferences, workshops, and standardization meetings (e.g., IETF, 3GPP, ETSI MEC ISG, 5GAA, Networld2020 meeting) to show-case the results of CODECO, provide tutorials, demos, etc..	At least 3 demonstrations per year, starting on year 2.	Use-case partners	5 demonstrations
SDO Liaison and monitoring	SDO, ICT, AR, GOV	Based on T6.3, assist the wider impact of CODECO via concrete contributions to SDOs (event organization, white papers, Standards).	>10 contributions	T6.3 partners	4 contributions

7 Next Steps: M19-M36

This section provides a summary of the steps being planned in terms of the major aspects concerning the dissemination, promotion, and scientific outreach as well as standardisation activities. While not intending to be exhaustive, the aim of the section is to prepare the CODECO outreach and engagement for the next period.

7.1 Public Dissemination and Communication

About the next actions concerning public dissemination and communication, the focus shall be on community engagement, given that CODECO has already demonstrated outreach capability in terms of scientific and industrial engagement. A summary of the current actions are as follows:

- **CODECO Website**, partner INO is proposing a restructuring with focus on IRCEP, regular updates to the News and an update of the Use-cases section, to accommodate videos currently under development, targeting EUS and ICT/AR.
- **Social media**, partner INO is proposing to focus on the dissemination of the CODECO use-cases latest developments (technical and marketing videos being developed by use-case leaders, cf. To Figure 9), and to start a series of CODECO key technological aspects posts, inviting specific partners to contribute to a brief overview on such aspects. Another aspect being handled is an improvement to X.
- **Project visual aspects**, partner FOR is preparing self-explanatory videos for the project and shall provide a global review of all CODECO material (flyers, brochures, etc.) to allow for the inclusion of the latest results, including OSS code.

Figure 9: Proposal for the dissemination of the CODECO use-cases via social media.

7.2 Broad Scientific and Innovation Outreach

Regarding the wider scientific and innovation outreach, the main aspects to be handled in CODECO are as follows:

- **Increase the number of scientific publications developed in partnership.** This will be developed together with WP5, based on a specific experimentation and validation plan being proposed by the WP5 leader, ATH.
- **Continue the development of the CODECO “Development events”,** namely, a Dagstuhl seminar organized by UGOE in cooperation with other partners and analysing with partners the possibility and relevancy to organize other similar scientific events. Concerning the Dagstuhl seminar, refer to section 7.2.1 for further details. Another event being proposed specifically targeting the stakeholder group DEV is a Hackathon. Refer to section 7.2.2 for details.

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- **Continue the development of the proposed standardisation plan**, now specifically increasing the focus towards contributions. Concerning the standardisation next steps, please refer to section 7.2.3.
- **Finalize the CODECO White paper on Edge-Cloud orchestration**, being jointly developed with the other Horizon Europe projects in the topic of cognitive continuum. Editors: John Soldatos, Rute C. Sofia.
- **Start the edition of a book on 6G Edge-Cloud Flexible Orchestration**, based on the debate held in the EUCNC CONASENSE 2024 workshop. Editors: Rute C. Sofia (FOR), Ramjee Prasad, Javier Serrano (UPM)

7.2.1 CODECO Development Event 2: Dagstuhl Seminar

Dagstuhl Seminars⁶¹ are a prestigious series of academic meetings held at Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz Center for Informatics in Germany.

The consortium is developing a proposal for a Dagstuhl Seminar to be submitted in November 2024 and expected to occur in the summer 2025. The seminar entitled “Edge-Cloud Data-Compute-Network Orchestration” is being planned as a three-day event which aims to bring together circa 40-45 participants from academia and industry to debate on AI-driven decentralization’s principles and challenges in orchestrating the Edge-Cloud continuum. Experts from academia and industry will convene to discuss novel aspects of Edge-Cloud orchestration, emphasizing AI’s role in supporting federated, multi-domain, multi-tenant environments.

A few research questions to be addressed in this seminar are: what are the key challenges for the upcoming next-generation Internet and IoT, that should be envisioned in this new Edge-Cloud continuum? What are the general principles of a computing-network-data continuum, and can such principles be addressed in a way that may support a generic design of an evolutionary, mobile, cognitive, and adaptive Edge-Cloud? Which orchestration solutions suit better a mobile and adaptive multi-tenant federated environment?

The organizers are:

- Tingting Yuan, Göttingen University, Germany
- Rute C. Sofia, Fortiss GmbH, Germany
- Tim Wood, George Washington University, United States
- Mianxiong Dong, Muroran Institute of Technology, Japan

A list of participants is being proposed, considering the different CODECO target stakeholder groups, involving junior and senior staff.

The seminar has the following objectives:

- To discuss and share the latest research and industry developments in AI-based, decentralized edge-cloud orchestration.
- To identify the research gaps and discuss potential solutions for challenges in the development of cognitive and decentralized edge-cloud orchestration.
- To promote an exchange of ideas so AI/ML researchers can better understand existing edge computing use-cases where Cloud-Edge-IoT architectures are being applied, and computer science researchers can learn how Edge-Cloud orchestration systems can benefit from data-driven intelligence.

⁶¹ <https://www.dagstuhl.de/de/seminars/dagstuhl-seminars>

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- To collect and document use cases, best practices, relevant data sets, and experiments derived from existing projects across different countries and world regions.
- To raise awareness and promote the practical applications of cognitive and decentralized edge-cloud orchestration in various fields such as healthcare, transportation, and smart cities.

7.2.2 CODECO Development Event 3: IETF Hackathon

In the context of the dissemination and communication, and the exploitation activities, it is necessary to engage our communities. Remote webinars, workshops, contests, or hackathons are great ways to raise awareness around CODECO and engage the developer community. A hackathon brings useful feedback in terms of how the project is understood, how the platform is used, etc.

The CODECO consortium has proposed to organize a Hackathon jointly between WP7 and WP6, and to be led in 2024 by partner ECL. The main objectives are to engage with the community and to start challenging the CODECO Toolkit.

This specific Hackathon targets the following CODECO target stakeholders' groups: DEV, AR, ICT, SDO and is being planned to be organized as part of the *Standards Development Organization (SDO) Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Hackathon*⁶² in the IETF meeting 121⁶³, in Dublin, Ireland, November 2nd-4th 2024.

IETF Hackathons encourage developers and subject matter experts to collaborate and develop utilities, ideas, sample code and solutions that show practical implementations of IETF standards and have a broad reach.

For the CODECO project, the selected challenges must be aligned with IETF topics and needs, connected to Internet standards, covering IETF needs and potentially targeting specific and relevant ***IETF Working Groups (WG)*** which are working on the topics/challenges we will define. Hence, the Hackathon is also relevant as a CODECO standardisation event (T6.3).

The preparation plan for the Hackathon is already active and summarized in Table 13.

Table 13: CODECO IETF Hackathon preparation plan.

Action	Deadline
Identification: Topics/CODECO Components/IETF WG	May - June 2024
Involve CODECO partners	May - June 2024
Present Hackathon plan in Porto Plenary meeting	June 19 th
Activate collaborators / Community of interest	June - July 2024
Hackathon advertisement (wiki registration, etc.)	September - October 2024
Logistics arrangements	September - October 2024
Anticipated Work on challenges - Development	October 2024
CODECO @ IETF Hackathon in Dublin	2 - 4 November 2024

⁶² <https://www.ietf.org/meeting/hackathons/>

⁶³ <https://www.ietf.org/meeting/121/>

7.2.3 Events in Planning

In addition to the CODECO development events, the consortium is already planning several key events:

- **HiPEAC 2025, Barcelona, Spain, January 2025.**
 - A workshop is being proposed together with other projects in the cognitive computing topic. Led by FOR, the participation of CODECO will count with demonstrations and talks.
 - A booth is being proposed by ECL, where CODECO can be shown along other projects being developed by ECL (who is a sponsor of HiPEAC 2025).
- **IEEE WPMC 2024 CONASENSE 6G-SAC Workshop, Noida, India, November 2024.** In cooperation with the 6G CONASENSE platform, FOR is chairing the CONASENSE 6G-SAC workshop, where a session will be dedicated to CODECO talks and demonstrations.
- **Eclipse Open-Source Experience (OCX 2024), Mainz, Germany.** Partner ECL is one of the organizers of the conference and expects to bring CODECO to one of the sessions.
- **RedHat Research Quarterly Talks**, online, November 2024. Partner RHT is proposing to debate CODECO in the internal quarterly talks, providing updates concerning the latest developments.

7.3 Standardisation

Concerning the plans for standardisation monitoring and contributions, Table 14 presents a summary of the expected next steps to be handled in the context of T6.3.

Table 14: Next steps in standardisation.

SDO	Partners	Identified liaison topics	Next Steps
BDVA	UPRC, ATOS, INTRA, I2CAT	A1.6, A4.1: Contributions to CODECO on AI engineering and trustworthiness aspects in data spaces	Partners to provide specific contributions being planned. Debate in the context of the component PDLC, identification of potential contributions towards specific standards.
CEN-CENELEC	I2CAT	A4.2: Contributions are also envisioned to CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 on AI PDLC	Meeting with I2CAT to understand potential contributions (M20)
ETSI	ICOM, TID/UC3M, UC3M	A1.1, A1.3, A1.5, A4.2, A4.3: -Contributions in the context of Cloud/Edge application of CODECO. <i>ACM, NetMA</i> -Contributions in intent-based Edge Service Management for resource and energy efficiency. <i>PDLC, NetMA</i> -Contributions in secure connectivity, <i>NetMA</i>	ETSI ENI: ICOM, TID, Contributions in intent-based Edge Service Management for resource and energy efficiency. <i>PDLC, NetMA</i>
IETF	TID/UC3M, FOR	A1.3, A1.4, A4.3: - CODECO application-network integration contributions to existing RFCs CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge services - CODECO extensions and support for decentralized Edge computing services. <i>NetMA; use-case requirements.</i>	FOR: IETF WG DetNetWiFi, revision of the submitted industrial applications communication requirements draft; review on energy awareness requirements. FOR: IETF WG DetNetWiFi, analysis of current standards with focus on Edge challenges. TID: IETF COINRG continuation of the contributions towards cooperating layered architectures for SDN (CLAS)

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IRTF	FOR, ATH	A6.1: - Integrate the CODECO findings about fields such as networking management; IoT; decentralised Internet services - DINRG <i>All components, experimentation</i>	FOR: presentation of CODECO in the - discussion with WG DINRG chairs ⁶⁴ on the topic of Internet decentralization
5GPPP NetWorld-Europe	FOR, I2CAT, ATOS, TID	A1.7: Integrate the CODECO ideas and the role of an automated management of containers in 5G interoperability support for Edge computing. <i>ACM</i>	Continue the development of contributions to the current SRIA.
AIOTI	FOR, ICOM	A1.7, A4.1, A4.3: - Raise awareness to the role of CODECO in the context of Smart Cities; integrate the cross-layer CODECO perspective on data management, computation, and networking. - CODECO use-cases and EdgeNet interconnections as a reference testbed, aligned with the AIOTI testbed methodology. <i>All components, use-case customization.</i>	-FOR, Contributions to the HLA report with an overview on the CODECO and other CEI architectures -ALL: AIOTI Days 2024, CODECO session. FOR, ATH: Contribute with update on the CODECO experimental framework and shared cloud space.
EUCEI	FOR, ATOS, ECL	A1.3, A1.7: Architecture, taxonomy, contributions to specific standards, white papers	Continue working on alignment towards a CEI reference architecture (FOR)
Gaia-X	FOR	A1.2: Contributions to network service composition models, based on the CODECO learnings; NetMA; MDM	To develop a CODECO white paper with alignment to Gaia-X (M20-M24, FOR).

8 Summary and Conclusions

This report demonstrates the CODECO's activities of dissemination, promotion, scientific outreach, and standardization developed during the first eighteen months of CODECO.

CODECO's dissemination activities aim at sharing project results widely, ensuring that products, knowledge, and best practices are effectively utilized. Targeting audiences such as the scientific community, legislators, and stakeholders, these activities both benefit from and contribute to the project's outcomes. Promotion activities helped to increase the project's visibility. They engage a more generic target audience, including the media and public opinion. Scientific outreach efforts create awareness about the project's goals, achievements, and impact among different stakeholders from academia and industry. The standardization activities, ensure compatibility and seamless integration across systems. Common standards update development, deployment, and management processes, leading to more efficient and reliable systems.

Overall, CODECO shows significant project which is relevant to the development of its second phase of operation, where an initial community is already engaging across the different proposed target stakeholders. The different groups now become more crucial as CODECO reaches a more mature phase of development, and where results can now be better demonstrated via specific experimentation and use-cases.

The report provides, in addition to achievements, an overview on the initial steps towards the plans for the second phase of development (M19-M36). The mentioned activities are regularly updated in CODECO, and shall be documented on the final report, D23, due in month 36.

These mentioned activities are updated during the lifetime of the CODECO project and will be conveyed in the next report.

⁶⁴ <https://www.irtf.org/dinrg.html>

References

- [1] Joana Rodrigues (Ed.), CODECO Deliverable D21 – Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan. (1.0). Zenodo, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940407>.

